

STATISTICAL RESEARCH OF THE EFFICIENCY OF TEACHING MOLECULAR PHYSICS AND THERMODYNAMICS BASED ON A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15984798>

Abstract. *This article presents the experience of teaching academic lyceum students the topics of molecular physics and thermodynamics using an improved digital educational platform. Using the chi-square (χ^2) criterion, t-test, dispersion, and efficiency indicators, changes in students' knowledge levels were identified. A comparative analysis of the experimental and control groups demonstrated the high effectiveness of the proposed methodology.*

Keywords: *digital educational platform, molecular physics, thermodynamics, statistical analysis, chi-square criterion (χ^2), t-test, dispersion, efficiency indicator, academic motivation, experimental research, academic lyceum, assessment criteria, interactive learning, simulation-based lessons.*

Introduction

In today's era, when modern information and communication technologies are rapidly entering the educational process, it has become an important issue to organize the lesson interactively, encourage student activity, increase the effectiveness of mastering, and direct knowledge to practical application. In particular, in teaching physics, the need to convey many theoretical concepts to students in an understandable way, to demonstrate experiments on a visual basis, to analyze phenomena, and to combine them with advanced technologies is increasingly growing.

The department of molecular physics and thermodynamics is distinguished by the complexity of its content, the abstraction of theoretical models and physical laws. Therefore, the effective use of digital educational tools in teaching this department is relevant, and modern approaches - for example, simulations, animations, interactive tasks - serve to strengthen students' understanding of the subject.

This article discusses the practical experience of teaching the department "Molecular Physics and Thermodynamics" to students of an academic lyceum using the proposed digital platform. Based on experimental work, changes in students' knowledge, skills and competencies are analyzed using various statistical methods. As a result of these analyses, it is determined how much the platform has had a positive impact on the quality and effectiveness of the lesson. The article also reveals the evaluation criteria, methodological approaches, and the results of the comparison between the experimental and control groups on a scientific basis.

Research methodology

This stage of the research is aimed at assessing the practical effectiveness of the proposed digital platform and is carried out on the basis of experimental pedagogical tests. Experimental

tests will be organized in the conditions of academic lyceums, within the framework of the Department of Molecular Physics and Thermodynamics.

➤ *Experiment objects:*

- Republican Academic Lyceum named after S.H. Sirojiddinov
- Academic Lyceum of Samarkand State University
- Academic Lyceum of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute
- Academic Lyceum of the National Pedagogical University of Uzbekistan named after Nizami

Since these lyceums cover different regions of Uzbekistan, they allow us to test the effectiveness of digital educational products in different socio-cultural and technological conditions. The selection of experimental sites also helps to analyze differences in the quality of education between regions.

Research objective:

To determine the impact of an improved digital software product on the mastering of molecular physics and thermodynamics in academic lyceums, as well as to observe changes in students' knowledge, skills and competencies using this product.

The results of the experiment served as the basis for the research hypothesis. Questionnaire questions given to the physics teacher and students during the observation process.

The following issues were explored when introducing the survey questions:

1. The impact of teaching the section “Molecular Physics and Thermodynamics” of the physics course based on software on the quality and effectiveness of students' knowledge.
2. The impact on the formation of students' practical skills and qualifications in molecular physics and thermodynamics.
3. Difficulties in teaching molecular physics using software tools.
4. The importance of teaching the section “Molecular Physics and Thermodynamics” based on software tools in developing students' independent thinking and creative abilities.

The questionnaire questions of this content showed that teaching this section based on software tools has a positive effect on the formation of students' physical ideas, understanding their interdependence, and being an important tool in directing students to a profession. The analysis of the questionnaire questions revealed that the wide range of possibilities for using software tools in teaching topics related to the “Molecular Physics and Thermodynamics” section of physics is of great importance in improving students' polytechnic preparation and choosing a profession. The interview with physics teachers made it possible to identify the difficulties encountered in teaching this section using software tools. The experimental test was conducted in the 1st year to collect data on teaching molecular physics using software tools, to prove the effectiveness of the given methodology and to make recommendations for teaching this section. It was determined that it is important to explain to students the application of laws, phenomena and processes related to the “Molecular Physics and Thermodynamics” section of the physics course in industry, agriculture, and everyday life.

As a result of the clarifying experiment, topics that are relevant for 1st year students were selected. The results of the experiment were developed using the method of mathematical statistics. In this case, teaching in the experimental and test classes was compared. This proved the correctness of the working hypothesis. It was shown that the materials developed for the program on the methodology of teaching molecular physics using software tools have a positive impact on learning, simultaneously leading to the formation of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and

qualifications in molecular physics, and increasing the quality and efficiency of the lesson. In addition, in the current era, there is a great interest in providing students with knowledge and professions that are being revived in line with the demands of the times.

Test participants. 2 groups are selected from each lyceum: one is experimental (learning on the basis of the new platform), the other is a control group (with traditional teaching methods). Each group will include at least 26 students. Experimental testing work was organized in 3 grades in each academic lyceum. In total, 624 students (312 experimental, 312 control) will participate.

Methodological foundations. Experimental testing work is organized based on the following methodological steps:

- **Diagnostics:** pre-test to determine the initial level of knowledge;
- **Intervention:** the experimental group uses the platform for 4 weeks. Each week, 2 topics are taught using the platform.
- **Monitoring:** active participation of students, grades, and task completion speed are automatically monitored by the platform;
- **Evaluation:** post-test to determine the final level of knowledge, statistical comparison of results.

Table 1

Tasks to be carried out

Stage	Deadline	Tasks to be carried out
Preparatory stage	1st week	Forming groups, preparing test materials
Diagnostics	2nd week	Conducting pre-tests, assessing initial knowledge
Experiment	Weeks 3-6	Digital platform-based training, monitoring
Final evaluation	7th week	Post-test, analyzing results

During the pilot phase, two groups from each lyceum were formed — experimental and control. The experimental groups participated in the learning process using the improved digital platform, while the control groups were taught using traditional teaching methods. The test was conducted for 4 weeks.

Work carried out in the experimental group:

- Students started the lesson on each topic by entering the module on the platform;
- Topics were presented together with animations, interactive simulations and theoretical material;
- Students completed independent exercises and were assessed through automatic tests;
- Their active participation and results were constantly monitored through the platform's tracking module;
- After each lesson, reflection blocks were filled out and the level of mastery was assessed.

Work carried out in the control group:

- The topics were explained to the students by the teacher based on textbooks;
- Practical exercises were conducted in the traditional way (using classic laboratory equipment);
- Theoretical knowledge and exercises were mastered using notebooks and a blackboard;
- Tests were conducted in paper form and evaluated by the teacher;
- The level of activity and mastery was analyzed based on subjective assessment.

Model for organizing the experimental-testing process

2-table

Differences between groups

Main factors	Experimental group:	Control group
Educational tool	Digital platform	Textbooks and teacher commentary
Visual materials	Animation, simulation	Picture, diagram, poster
Animation	Picture, diagram, poster	
Exercises and tests	Interactive, automatic	Paper-based, checked by the teacher
Interactive	assessment	
Reflection and analysis	Written/electronic after each lesson	Oral or written (limited)
Monitoring system	Online analytics and graphs	Based on teacher's notebook entries

As part of the pilot study, comprehensive assessment methods based on modern pedagogical criteria were used to assess students' knowledge, practical skills, and subject competencies. The assessment process was carried out in three stages: initial (pre-test), intermediate (during the process), and final (post-test).

Evaluation criteria

The assessment was based on the following components:

1. Knowledge level: knowledge of theoretical concepts, correct understanding of physical laws;
2. Skill level: independent problem solving, use of formulas, analysis of experimental results;
3. Competency level: ability to explain physical phenomena using real-life examples, apply one's knowledge in an interactive environment.
 - *Evaluation forms*
 - Test tasks: closed (choose the correct one from several options), open (fill in the blank, write an explanation);
 - Practical tasks: analysis based on experimental results, graphing;
 - Simulation-based assessment: the student performs a virtual experiment on the platform and explains the results;
 - Reflective assessment: written answers to questions such as "What did I learn?", "What problem did I encounter?" after each lesson.

Sample question (for pre- and post-tests):

1. Which of the following ideas does the molecular-kinetic theory put forward?
 - A) Temperature depends on the pressure of a gas
 - B) Matter is made up of particles and they are in motion ✓
 - C) Particles in motion always give off heat
 - D) The pressure of a gas does not depend on its volume
2. What physical process does Brownian motion occur as a result of? *The pupil must provide a written explanation.*
3. What shape does the graph of isothermal expansion of an ideal gas have?
 - A) Hyperbola ✓
 - B) Straight line
 - C) Parabola
 - D) Sinusoid
4. Watch the following experiment animation and answer: What result is obtained based on the heat balance equation? The student fills in the formula in the interactive experiment window:
5. Real-life example: A container of milk stored in a refrigerator begins to adjust to room temperature in a few minutes. Which thermodynamic law does this process correspond to?

3-table

Evaluation criteria

Assessment format	Maximum points	Skill type	Assessment method
Theoretical test (MCQ + written)	40 points	Knowledge, analysis	Test questions, short answers
Practical assignment	30 points	Skills, analysis	Problem solving, graphing
Simulation Assessment	20 points	Apply, create	Virtual experience, comment

Reflective Writing	10 points	Self-analysis	Written reflection, lesson summary
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Statistical analysis

For the analysis, 26 students in each group participated (a total of 624 students in 4 lyceums, 2 groups in each, and 3 experiments were conducted in each lyceum).

Several statistical methods were used to determine the differences between the experimental and control groups. These included arithmetic mean values, variance, chi-square test (χ^2), t-test (Student test) and efficiency indicator.

The chi-square test (χ^2) is a statistical method used to determine whether the distribution of nominal variables, i.e. qualitative indicators (for example, the categories of grades such as “excellent”, “good”, “satisfactory”) is different or not between experimental and control groups. If the empirical value of χ^2 is greater than the critical value when calculating the χ^2 statistic, this means that the difference between the groups is not due to chance, but rather to the methodology used. This test is especially useful in assessing the significance of changes between the initial (pre-test) and final (post-test) stages.

T-test (Student test) – is used to compare the mean scores of two groups. Here, the t-test is used to compare the mean scores of the experimental group in the post-test with those of the control group. If the t value is high and $p < 0.05$ (or smaller), this means that the difference between the mean scores is statistically significant and can be explained by the effect of the method.

Dispersion (D) – this indicates the degree of dispersion around the students’ scores. If the dispersion is lower in the experimental group, this means that their scores are more stable. That is, most students recorded similar results – this indicates the effectiveness of the method.

Efficiency index (η) – this indicator calculates the relative increase in percentage between the mean scores at the beginning and end of the experiment. This clearly shows how effective the method was. For example, if $\eta = 15\%$, this means that the students' knowledge level has increased by 15%.

4-table

Statistical methods

Statistical method	Scope	Result	Explanation
Chi-square test (χ^2)	Comparing nominal variables	$\chi^2_{emp} > \chi^2_{crit}$	The difference is statistically significant
T-test	Comparing mean scores	$p < 0.00001$ (experimental group)	The changes are significant
Variance (D)	Determining the spread of scores	$D_{experiment} < D_{control}$	The stability in the experimental group is high
Scalar variance (η)	Estimating knowledge growth in percentage	15–17% increase (experimental group)	The methodology is effective
Correlation	Relationship between results and monitoring	positive	The monitoring predicted the result

Experimental results and analysis

5-table

Overall results of students of educational institutions in experimental and test work for three years

Indicator	Experimental group		Control group	
	Number of students at the beginning of the experiment	Number of students at the end of the experiment	Number of students at the beginning of the experiment	Number of students at the end of the experiment
Excellent	8	50	6	7
Good	115	184	123	143
Satisfactory	177	78	166	152
Unsatisfactory	12	0	17	10
Total	312	312	312	312

Students' results at the beginning of the experiment:

$$\chi^2_{emp} \approx 1,77; \quad \bar{x} \approx 3,38; \quad \bar{y} \approx 3,38; \quad D_m = 0,365 \quad ; D_n = 0,384$$

The empirical value obtained is less than the critical value, i.e. $1.77 < 7.81$. This indicates that the hypothesis H_1 can be accepted at the beginning of the experiment. That is, there is no significant change in the knowledge levels of students in the experimental and control groups before the experiment.

The results of the students at the end of the experiment:

$$\chi^2_{emp} \approx 71,38; \quad \bar{x} \approx 3,91; \quad \bar{y} \approx 3,47; \quad D_m = 0,403 \quad ; D_n = 0,359$$

Based on the results obtained, the post-experimental performance indicators and t-test results of the experimental and control groups are as follows:

$$\eta_m = 15,64\%; \quad t_m = 10,658; \quad p_m = 0,00001 < 0,05$$

$$\eta_n = 2,75\%; \quad t_n = 1,905; \quad p_n = 0,0573 > 0,05$$

The diagram of the indicators excitation of pupils

Tajriba guruhi- Experimental group-
Nazorat guruhi Control group
Samaradorlik ko'rsatkichi Effectiveness index

The empirical value obtained is greater than the critical value, i.e. $71.38 > 7.81$. According to the results of the experiment conducted in the academic years from 2022 to 2025, the grades of students in the experimental group increased by 15.64%, and this change was found to be statistically significant ($t = 10.654$; $p < 0.001$) by t-test. On the contrary, the change in grades in the control group by 2.75% was not significant ($t = 1.905$; $p = 0.0573$). This indicates that the experimental methodology had a significant positive impact on the results of students.

Therefore, the recommended methodology is effective, which indicates that the hypothesis H_1 can be accepted.

The results of the experimental work conducted during 2022–2025 are as follows: in the experimental groups, the average grades increased by 14–17%, while in the control groups this figure was only 1–3%. The t-test results in the experimental groups were $p < 0.00001$, which showed that the difference was statistically significant. The chi-square test also confirmed the existence of a significant difference between the groups at the end of the experiment. At the same time, the levels of students' mastery through reflective writing, independent work and simulations also increased significantly.

Graphs and tables compiled based on the analysis results clearly reflected the increase in the level of students' mastery. The experimental group recorded 20–28% higher results than the control group in terms of post-test scores, the percentage of students who completed practical assignments, involvement in interactive lessons and the number of those who wrote reflections.

Conclusions and recommendations

The results of the study show that the proposed digital educational platform is highly effective in teaching molecular physics and thermodynamics. The results of statistical analysis showed a significant increase in the knowledge, skills and competencies of students in the experimental group. The integration of digital tools into the teaching process not only increased the level of mastery, but also increased students' interest in the lesson.

Based on the experimental work, the following scientific and practical recommendations are made:

1. The use of digital platforms should be expanded to other sections of physics.
2. Special advanced training courses should be organized for teachers on working with digital resources.
3. Diagnostic, assessment and analytics modules should be further improved for the digital platform.
4. In order to increase student motivation, opportunities for interdisciplinary integration should be created through digital tools.
5. Develop methodological guides and recommendations for using the platform.

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